

Comparative Study of Development in Techniques for Smart Detection of Fire

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Abstract— The progress on fire detection technologies has been substantial over the last decade due to advances in sensor, microelectronics, and information technologies, as well as a greater understanding of fire physics. This paper provides a review of progress in fire detection technologies over the last decade, including various emerging sensor technologies (e.g., computer vision system, distributed fiber optic temperature sensor, and intelligent multiple sensors), signal processing, and monitoring technology (e.g., real-time control via the Internet) and integrated fire detection systems. Some problems and future research efforts related to current fire detection technologies are discussed.

Keywords—Fire Detection, Distributed Fiber Optic Temperature Sensor, Intelligent Multiple Sensors

I. INTRODUCTION

With advances in sensors, microelectronics, and information technologies, as well as a greater understanding of fire physics, many new fire detection technologies and concepts have been developed over the last decade. For example, techniques are available now for measuring almost any stable gaseous species produced before or during combustion [1]. The distributed fiber optic temperature sensors have been introduced to provide fire protection for those applications with difficult ambient conditions such as tunnels, underground railways, and stations [2]. More than one fire signature detected by multiple sensors, such as smoke, heat, and CO signatures can be processed at the same time through an intelligent algorithm to intelligently discriminate between fire and non-threatening or deceptive conditions [3]. In addition, fire detection systems are integrated with other building service systems to reduce false

alarms, speed building evacuation, and assist in firefighting.

Over the last decade, however, insulation and building materials, furnishings, and furniture have undergone a major transformation from natural materials, such as wood and cotton, to synthetic materials. Consequently, the risk to life and property has changed radically since burning synthetic materials releases not only highly dangerous smoke and toxic fumes but also carbon monoxide at rates far over natural materials [4], resulting in a dramatic reduction in the available time for escape. Many of the locations in most need of protection, such as telecommunication facilities, are unattended and/or remote [5], and interruptions to the service caused by fires are becoming more costly.

Fire detection technology still faces challenges related to reducing false alarms, increasing sensitivity and dynamic response, as well as providing protections for highly expensive and complex installations to better safeguard the public and meet evolving regulations. This paper aims to review recent research and development in fire detection technology, including emerging sensor technology, fire signal processing, and monitoring technology, and integrated fire detection system. Some problems and future activities related to fire detection technology are discussed.

II. EMERGING SENSOR TECHNOLOGY

A. Heat Detectors

The distributed fiber optic temperature sensor is considered as one of the new and promising heat detection technologies for fire protection applications [2]-[6]. Optic fiber has been widely used for the transmission of information, and it can also be used for sensing changes in temperature, strain, and tensile force subjected to the fiber optic cable, as the variation of these physical parameters alters the refractive indices and geometric properties of the optical fiber and then perturbs the intensity, phase, or polarization of the light wave propagating within the optical fiber. Unlike the conventional thermal detectors, the distributed optical fiber sensor uses the entire optical fiber as the sensing medium. Temperature measurements can be made at any and every point along the fiber cable. The measured temperature is in the range of -160 to 800o C, which is limited only by the durability of the fiber, or more specifically, its primary coating. In comparison to conventional thermal detectors, the optical fiber sensor cable responds much more quickly to temperature fluctuations due to its low mass. The fiber cable itself is strong, resilient,

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flexible for different geometry, and can be directly placed near or into protected facilities. It is also immune to all kinds of interference emissions. Conceivably, the location, size, and development of a fire can be determined with higher spatial and temperature resolutions and unmatched flexibility in measurement locations. The distributed fiber optic temperature sensors based on Rayleigh and Raman scattering were introduced for fire detection in the late 1980s. They have been used to provide fire protection for those applications with difficult ambient conditions such as tunnels, underground railways and stations, conveyor lines, steelworks, and petrochemical plants.

The distributed fiber optic sensor system based on Raman scattering detects the temperature by measuring the ratio of the Stokes to anti-Stokes backscattered intensity signal as a function of temperature. The system uses a bare multi-mode fiber or the fiber encapsulated within a suitable cable sheath. The level of the Raman-scattering signal is weak, which restricts the sensing range and spatial resolution of the Raman scattering system. A long integration time is needed. The maximum sensing range of the current Raman system is up to 4 km and its spatial resolution varies from 8 m to 1 m, depending on the requirement for response time and temperature resolution.

B. Smoke Detectors

Smoke is produced much earlier than other fire signatures during the stages of fire growth and development. The rapid detection of smoke at very low levels can maximize the probability of successful fire suppression, escape, and survivability. Smoke can be sensed from the interaction of the particles with a beam of light or electromagnetic

radiation. The mass concentration, volume fraction, and size distribution of the smoke are identified as key parameters for smoke detection [8]. A smoke detector must be capable of responding to smoke from both smoldering and flaming combustion because the smokes from these fires are significantly different in structure and composition [9].

Smoke from a smoldering fire tends to have bigger particles of combustion products than those generated from flaming combustion. The detector may be located at the sensing location (spot detector) or a remote location with the smoke pumped to the detector.

C. Flame Detectors

The fire, itself, is a source of radiation, and it can be detected by the recognition of radiation produced in the burning zone [10]. Currently, there are two types of flame detectors based on the measurement of the range of flame radiation: infra-red detector and ultra-violet detector. Infra-red detectors (IR) detect fires when a characteristic flame flicker produced by fire is received, while ultra-violet detectors (UV) detect fires when any ultra-violet radiation produced by flaming combustion is detected. Flame detectors

can be used to protect large areas and they have a rapid response because they do not have to rely on smoke or heat from the fire. They can also be used in the open air, unlike the smoke detectors that need a ceiling to function effectively. However, false alarms may be generated by radiation from other sources such as welding, sunlight, and tungsten lamps.

Efforts have been made to minimize nuisance alarms by IR and UV detectors, by combining multi-wavelength radiation sensing with algorithms that determine object temperature, flame temperature, surface area, and presence of a flame. The combination ultraviolet/infrared (UV/IR) flame detector significantly reduces the spurious alarm problems associated with the old UV detectors. Because the UV/IR flame detector detects both UV and IR radiation emitted from the flames, it prevents the false alarm from other common sources of ultraviolet radiation other than a flame that does not emit infrared radiation at 4.3 μm [11]. The UV/IR detector, however, still depends on the vacuum photodiode tube to detect ultraviolet radiation. It has failure-to-alarm problems associated with the absorption of ultraviolet radiation by aerosols such as smoke or vapors in the air, or liquid and solid contaminants on the detector window.

The dual-wave-length infrared (IR/IR) flame detector abandons the ultraviolet portion of the spectrum entirely and operates in the infrared portion of the spectrum. It detects the flaming combustion of hydrocarbons by comparing the radiant intensity typically at 4.2 - 4.7 μm (emitted by CO₂) with the radiant intensity at the reference wavelength of 3.8 - 4.1 μm (near the CO₂ peak) that serves as background energy monitoring [36]. The IR/IR flame detector eliminates the interference of smoke as well as the liquid and solid contaminants on the detector window. However, two factors limit the detection range of the dual IR detector. The first one is that the fire radiation intensity around 4.3 μm significantly decreases as the distance increases. The second one is that the ratio between the 4.3 μm spectral band released from the fire and the 4.0 μm spectral band used as the reference background approaches equality, which could give no fire signal when the algorithm processes the fire signals. To overcome the drawbacks of dual IR detectors, a triple IR flame detector has recently been developed [12]. The triple IR detector utilizes a combination of three IR sensors of extremely narrow band response: one covering the typical CO₂ flame emission spectral band, and the two others covering different adjacent specially-selected spectral bands. The high sensitivity of the triple IR detector is achieved by extracting extremely low signals deeply buried in noise by adopting digital correlation techniques. The triple IR detector does not produce any false alarm to any continuous, modulated, or pulsating radiation sources other than fires. It offers an extended detection range up to 60 m, compared to 15-20 m for the standard optical flame detector [13]. The triple IR flame detector has been used in rough working conditions where all types of flames need to be detected during day or night, under hot or cold, dry or wet weather conditions.

CCTV (Closed Circuit Television) technology has a great advantage for use in sensing and monitoring a fire. Compared with other types of fire detectors, the video cameras cannot be fooled by visible, or emissions from common background sources, eliminating false alarm problems. It processes multiple spectral images in real-time to reliably detect a small fire or smoke at greater distances in very short times, and at the same time, it can identify the location of a fire, track its growth and monitor fire suppression. It can be trained for very rapid response, making it suitable for explosion suppression systems. The application areas for video fire detection systems are developing fast. Detecting smoke plumes in forests and fires in aircraft hangars have been the first applications.

D. Gas Sensors

Since gases are produced in all stages of combustion, a specific gas signature could be used for reliable fire detection. Jackson and Robins [14] measured CO, CO₂, H₂, O₂, and smoke density generated by open cellulose fires (wood), smoldering pyrolysis (cellulosic), and cotton fires, open plastic fire (polyurethane), and liquid n-heptane and methylated spirit fires. Their research showed that there were large differences in the chemical composition of the smoke involving different types of fires. Of the four warning gases, the best was carbon monoxide that was presented in all six types of fires. Its concentration was high in relatively slow-burning fires and low in faster burning fires. There were also large differences in the oxygen concentrations involving six types of fires in which the oxygen concentrations changed significantly when involving faster burning fires, such as liquid fuel fires, while the change in the oxygen concentration was hardly detected when involving smoldering fires. Based on test results, they believed that gas sensors can be used not only for fire detection but they can also be used to provide information on whether the fire is flaming, smoldering, or intermediate.

Techniques are available now for measuring almost any stable gaseous species produced before or during combustion [1]. Chemical species can be sensed through a multitude of interactions, including catalytic, electrochemical, mechanic-chemical, and optical processes. However, many of the gases generated during the combustion process also occur naturally or are generated in non-threatening combustion processes. In addition, to detect specific gas signatures, the sensor needs a significant power source, which restricts it as a cost-effective fire detector.

III. SIGNAL PROCESSING AND MONITORING TECHNOLOGY

With the introduction of artificial intelligence techniques, the effectiveness of fire detection technology is significantly enhanced. The fire signal received by the sensor is processed by the microcomputer-based technology (software algorithms) and compared with known information and a

database of generic fire signatures, and then an output response based on the total quantity of available information is generated. More than one fire signature detected by multiple sensors, such as smoke, heat, and CO signatures can be processed at the same time through an intelligent algorithm [3]-[15]. Meacham [16] has summarized the intelligent algorithms used for fire detection, including cross-correlation, algorithmic comparison, neural networks, and fuzzy reasoning. Some new fire detection algorithms, such as the Hidden Markov Model based on a signal classification principle [17], are also being developed. Advance in artificial intelligence techniques and semiconductor technology allows the fire detection system to accurately and intelligently discriminate between fire and non-threatening or deceptive conditions; to be sensitive to a variety of fires; to be used in monitoring the fire development; and to provide possible environmental compensation and continually adjust for temperature changes, dust, and dirt accumulation, humidity, voltage fluctuations, and component aging. All factors hurting the detector is sensitivity and contributing to false alarms. Intelligent fire detection systems now represent approximately 50% by value of all new systems installed worldwide [18].

Currently, there are two types of intelligent fire detection systems: one is where the fire signal processing and decision making are carried out in the detector and the other is where the fire identification and decision making are carried out in the panel. For medium to large fire detection systems, intelligence in the panel is a cost-effective selection. Detectors that do not contain a microprocessor and associated support circuitry are less complex and more reliable. The powerful central processing unit (CPU) can be fitted into the control panel to allow the system to use complex algorithms and advanced signal processing for fire signature identification. Many addressable multiple sensors at different locations will be able to connect and transmit separate sensitivity information to the panel for processing and decision making. This may enhance fire detection capability while at the same time lowering total system costs, because the sensor primarily used for another purpose may provide useful information related to early fire detection. Higher than expected levels of CO₂, for example, maybe a sign of poor air circulation within a room, but may also be the signs of a fire. Similarly, parameters such as temperature and air movement can be used for the maintenance of the indoor working environment but also fire detection purposes. Various inputs, such as thermal, smoke, CO, and CO₂, provided by the distributed sensors to the control panel would be expected to reduce the rate of false alarms and increase the speed of detection of real problems. The study carried out by Cleary and Notarianni [19] has demonstrated that such distributed sensing may improve time to alarm over single-station detectors.

Most commercial monitoring systems use a modem and remote dial-up to access the building's operating system. Studies have been carried out to do real-time control of a

building automation system via the Internet [20]. Compared to a voice/touch-tone interface, the Internet can provide more information (text, images, and sound clips).

The City University of Hong Kong has carried out an initial research project to use the Internet for real-time control of building automation systems. One air-handling unit (AHU) simulator was used in the test. A camera was used to monitor AHU so that the operation of AHU can be monitored through the Internet. Every User around the world can retrieve the updated status from 23 analog and digital points, such as temperature and humidity. The user, through the Internet, is also able to send commands to the simulator to operate any one actuator by simply clicking the scroll bar. Their study has shown that the Internet has the potential to extend the monitoring and control of a typical building automation system so that users can gain access to it at any time and from anywhere. Their work also showed that one central 24-hour management office can manage a real estate portfolio with hundreds of buildings.

A. Integrated Fire Detection System

The integration of a fire detection system with other building systems on a common backbone will allow the building systems to communicate with each other. The fire messages will be released not only from fire detection systems but also from other building systems. They will have priority at all times in the network. The decision-making components of the integrated system will assess the conditions and then determine what actions are required based on the sensor data. The appropriate commands that will be sent to the system are transducers and control devices. Once a fire occurs in a building, fire detection and alarm systems in buildings will be able to activate various fire safety systems, such as smoke control, and various pressurization and smoke exhaust systems. They will also activate elevator recall, the door release systems, flashing exit signs, and fire suppression systems. The integrated systems have the potential for reducing false alarms, speeding building evacuation, and assisting in firefighting. These changes will increase the level of protection to life and property and create new markets for fire detection, alarm, and fighting systems. As these technologies mature, changes to building practices may also result. Another push to integrate the fire detection system with other building systems is that the new generation of the building is expected to add the capability to learn about the building's circumstances and its occupant's needs and change the behavior of its control systems. For example, the building will use sensors to identify how a particular person tends to react to particular circumstances and to learn different behaviors from different people. To do this, a large number of sensors within the building will be required to operate the building responsively, rather than using pre-programmed control models. This will increase the cost of buildings and make it difficult to manage the resulting large

amount of data. However, when various types of sensors are integrated to be used as a multi-function sensor, the number of sensors required for monitoring the building environment will be reduced and the amount of data that needs to be processed will also be reduced.

Figure 1: Integrated Fire Detection System

Advantages of Intelligent Fire Systems in Complex and Large Buildings

- Addressable fire alarm systems give information about individual detectors, whereas conventional systems only give information about specific circuits (zones).
- Addressable systems allow a courtesy text label to allow easy identification of any event. For instance, detector 1 may be given the label 'Bedroom 1'.
- Most addressable systems allow an early 'pre alarm' warning, which allows the responsible person to investigate potential alarms before the system activates its sirens.
- Many addressable systems can alter the alarm threshold of the detectors, to meet the needs of different environments in different areas of the system.
- Addressable systems are usually wired in a loop.
- Conventional systems are usually wired as radial circuits.
- Addressable systems usually have a real-time clock & event log to record system events.
- Larger addressable systems usually can use sophisticated programming options to operate certain outputs only with specific events

Table 1: Summary of the previous study in the fire detection system

Ref.	Method/Techniques	Software/Component Used	Purpose
[2]	Distributed Temperature Sensing Optical Frequency Domain Reflectometry	Temperature Sensor	Show that pre-installed communication cables can be successfully used as automatic fire detection systems.
[3]	Intelligent	Smoke Alarm, Flame Detectors, Heat Detectors	The primary purpose of a fire alarm system is to provide an early warning of fire so that people can be evacuated & immediate action can be taken to stop or eliminate the fire effect as soon as possible.
[7]	Wireless Sensor Network	Raspberry Pi, Gas Sensor, Temperature Sensor	Proposed a prototype of a fire detection system based on WSN, this system takes advantage of WSN such as the facility of deployment, flexibility, and extensibility to allow early fire warning.
[8]	Image Processing	Camera, Raspberry pi	Proposed the low-cost development of early fire detection and surveillance system based on image processing.
[9]	Video Processing, color-based pixel classification,	MATLAB	Proposed a video-based early fire detection system.
[10]	Image Processing, Convolutional Neural Network	Python, TensorFlow, Camera	Proposed the model for classifying fire and smoke images captured by a camera or nearby surveillance systems.
[11]	GasFET-array	Metal Oxide Sensors	In this study, it is observed that the specific metal oxide sensors, gas-sensitive field-effect transistors, and electrochemical cells are well suited to be used for fire gas detection.
[13]	Haar Cascade Classifier	Camera, MATLAB	Proposed the deep learning technique for fire detection.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Many new fire detection technologies developed over the last decade have strong potential to reduce false alarms, increase sensitivity and dynamic response to fire and improve fire safety. The Brillouin scattering-based distributed fiber optic sensors have a long sensing range, responds quickly to temperature fluctuation, and is immune to all kinds of interference emission. It has the potential to provide fire detection in applications where small fires might be encountered (e.g., telecommunication facilities), and areas with restricted access or with difficult ambient conditions (e.g., tunnels, underground railways and stations, nuclear and petrochemical plants). However, further research efforts are needed to improve its spatial resolution and establish a cost-effective and reliable distributed fiber-optic system for fire detection.

Video fire detection systems have also demonstrated great advantages for use in sensing and monitoring a fire as well as on multi-function applications. Cameras and corresponding facilities required in the video sensor system are already standard features of many buildings. With further development in microelectronics and information technologies, video information can be sent out or accessed via the Internet or a wireless network. It is expected that the video sensor system will play a more important role in providing cost-effective fire safety and other building management and services.

In recent years, fire detectors tend to be more intelligent in discriminating between fire and non-threatening or deceptive conditions due to the introduction of artificial intelligent techniques as well as the development of microelectronics

technology. Multiple sensors that combine smoke and thermal sensors or CO sensor are capable of overcoming the drawbacks of single sensors in fire detection and provide better fire detection by discriminating many nuisance sources and extending detection capability for many fire sources.

The use of advanced control panels with advanced fire signal processing and sensor-driven fire model would substantially reduce false alarms and provide more accurate information on fire and smoke spread in the building. This will allow building operators and firefighters to make a more accurate and responsive evaluation of any fire-related incident in the building and to control fires and supervise the evacuation from the building more efficiently.

The use of real-time control via the Internet or wireless network will extend the monitoring and control of fire safety systems outside of the building. The status of the fire safety system and other building systems can be monitored at any time and from anywhere via the Internet or wireless network. The fire safety systems located in many buildings will be controlled from one central facility office. This will increase the efficiency and reduce costs for building management operations, more efficiently discriminate between fire and non-fire threats, and increase the time available for property and life protection. However, Internet-based monitoring and control of building service systems will need security protection to prevent false fire information from being provided to building owners and fire brigades.

The integration of fire detection and alarm systems with other building systems should increase fire safety in the building. The fire detection system will be able to communicate with other building systems, correctly discriminate between fire

and non-fire threats, identify the exact location of a fire in the building and provide continuous estimates on smoke and fire spread in the building. However, the integration technology may also create new risks. Sensor technologies, for example, will need to be robust enough to prevent false alarms and ensure that vital information such as the location of occupants is not lost due to data overload during a fire. Integrated building systems will need to be designed not only to give fire safety priority over other building activities but also that fire emergencies do not crash the building service system.

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